

Data for Generations

Archiving agricultural data to make it FAIR in the long run

Nikolai Svoboda*¹, Marcus Schmidt*, Kristin Meier*, Marcel Wallschläger*, Uta Parmaksiz**, Alfred Wutschka**, Katharina Markus**

*Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), ¹ svoboda@zalf.de

**Information Centre Life Science (ZB MED)

Agricultural Data becomes FAIR+

Research data published in the BonaRes Repository is not only FAIR but securely stored and available beyond the usual 10 years (FAIR+).

The key is professional archiving of research data previously published in the BonaRes Repository.

All research data that is provided with a DOI, making it citable and reusable, will be prepared for long term archiving (LTA) and submitted to the external infrastructure provided by ZB MED.

LTA makes all research data available eternally.

General workflow of archiving
*OAIS: Open Archival Information System

Archiving workflow

- DOI provision: trigger
- Automatic transfer to archive infrastructure based on Rosetta (ExLibris)
- Metadata mapping
 - BonaRes → Dublin Core (archival metadata standard)
- Rosetta
 - generates and stores preservation metadata (PREMIS standard)
 - structures metadata types (METS standard)
- Successful OAIS-compliant digital long-term archiving of agricultural research data will be recorded in ticket system
- Update of data and metadata if changes become necessary
- Retransfer: If required, data, metadata and supplementary material

Technical implementation: there and back gain
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Successfully overcome challenges

- Legal basis (contract) and resources allocation
- Decision on data to be archived
- Metadata mapping
- Technical implementation: transfer, interfaces; updates and versions

Next steps

- Improving complex data collections (dependencies between single data)
- Exploring the recovery workflow: DIP to Repository
- Fostering automatization
- Pre-ingest quality control

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